

Research Paper

Health Inspections of Restaurant Establishments in the Attica Region, Greece. Non-compliance Data Within the Food Hygiene Sector

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ABSTRACT

Background: Ensuring food safety is a fundamental priority for public health. The catering sector has become prominent as a convenient and cost-effective method of food supply worldwide. Adherence to proper food hygiene practices is crucial for preventing foodborne diseases. The inspection of food items is a key component of internal controls that enables the identification of non-compliance with food hygiene standards. The present study aims to assess Attica restaurant businesses' compliance with international food hygiene standards (FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius) and European legislation on unsafe food.

Methods: From January to July 2023, 74 randomly selected restaurants of small, medium, and large capacity in Attica were examined through inspections in terms of compliance for food hygiene standards. The inspections were based on (a) the completion of forms and (b) the collection of water and food samples for laboratory microbiological analysis.

Data were collected using a predefined form, referencing the manual of Codex Alimentarius regarding food hygiene standards (CAC/RCP 1-1969/CAC/RCP 39-1993). Additionally, the assessment included the identification of unsafe food placement in accordance with Regulation EC/178/2002 on food safety, as well as Greek national legislation (European Commission, 2002; Hellenic Republic, 2006, 2014).

Results: The highest non-compliance rates are in "adequacy of facilities" (14.12%), "equipment maintenance and sanitization" (12.30%), "pest control" (12.45%), "personal hygiene" (7.58%), and "efficient separation of raw materials" (9.76%). Non-compliance rates for other food hygiene parameters (cooking practices, meal apportionment, storage, transport, reheating, etc.) were considerably lower. The inspection results showed that medium-sized restaurant businesses present the highest rate (56.41%) of total non-compliance compared to large-sized businesses (29.68%) and small-sized businesses (13.91%).

Conclusions: This study demonstrates that restaurant businesses generally adhere to food hygiene and safety standards at a satisfactory level. There is a need for restaurant operators to prioritize enhancing compliance, particularly in addressing critical issues that could potentially result in outbreaks of foodborne diseases.

Food safety constitutes a key priority for public health. Unsafe food containing harmful micro-organisms (bacteria, viruses, parasites, etc.)

or chemical compounds may cause various illnesses and even death (World Health Organization, 2017). It is estimated that most of the

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foodborne diseases costing the lives of approximately 1.8 million people each year occur because of contaminated water or food (World Health Organization, 2015). Effective compliance with good food hygiene practices is vital for the prevention of these adverse consequences for people's health (Codex Alimentarius, 2023).

Food inspection constitutes a mandatory measure not only within the framework of internal controls but also during official controls by the competent authorities and aims at ensuring that all foods are safe, healthy, and suitable for consumer consumption throughout the production, handling, storage, food processing, and distribution processes. They also ensure that they comply with the food safety requirements and that they are clearly and accurately labeled as set out in the general food law Regulation (Makhunga et al., 2019).

Due to the increased urbanization, industrialization, and tourism, the catering sector has gained prominence throughout the world as a convenient and cost-effective means of food supply for a large number of people (Charles, 1983). Epidemiological surveillance indicates cases of foodborne disease caused by foods prepared by catering businesses exposing vulnerable populations, such as children, elderly people, patients, immunosuppressed individuals, etc., to the risk of foodborne disease (Codex Alimentarius, 1993). Even following a considerable time after the mandatory implementation of HACCP principles in Europe as set out in Regulation (EC) No 852/2004, foodborne disease outbreaks involving foods made available by food businesses have been reported (European Food Safety Authority & European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2017; Osimani et al., 2018). Food Business Operators (FBOs) should adhere to the required procedures and implement the necessary control measures to reduce or eliminate risk factors within their business and to ensure that foods placed on the market are safe and healthy (Codex Alimentarius, 2023; Regulation EC/852/2004). Inspections are a key element of internal controls and play a vital role in food safety (Kosola et al., 2022; Tabak & Ergun, 2022). Most cases of non-compliance are detected during the inspection of restaurant facilities (Yapp & Fairman, 2006). Codex Alimentarius FAO/WHO focuses on the development of food standards based on risk analysis and independent scientific advice from expert bodies established by the Food and Agriculture Organization and the World Health Organization (Rustia et al., 2021). It has been noticed that high levels of compliance with hygiene standards minimize food spoilage and contribute to ensuring food hygiene (Rotich et al., 2017).

The prefecture of Attica, encompassing the capital city of Athens and populous suburban municipalities like Piraeus, has the highest proportion of permanent residents in Greece (ELSTAT, 2021). Greece constitutes one of the greatest tourist destinations in the world. More than 30 million people visited Greece during the summer period of 2022. Attica is among the top five destinations in Greece based on data provided on the arrivals of air passengers in Greece (Institute of the Association of Greek tourism enterprises, 2022). In Greece, 2 foodborne outbreaks have been reported for 2024, but they do not involve the food businesses included in our survey.

According to the Greek legislation, restaurant businesses are divided into full-service restaurants (FSRs), (restaurants, pizzerias, rotisserie restaurants, steakhouses, Greek restaurants (tavernas), beer bars, snack bars, ouzo restaurants) or quick service restaurants (QSRs), (bars, cafeterias, creperies, bougatsa shops, canteens, ice cream stores, pastry shops), (Hellenic Republic, 2017); they are also placed into categories based on size (small: 01-50 employees, medium: 51-250 employees, large: over 251 employees), (Hellenic Republic, 2020).

The aim of this study was to evaluate the adherence of the above-mentioned categories of restaurant businesses in Attica to international standards, specifically the FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius standards, regarding food hygiene. Additionally, the study aims to assess compliance with the directives for implementing European legislation on unsafe food by restaurants.

Materials and methods

Data collection. From January to July 2023, inspections were conducted on 74 randomly selected restaurants with small, medium, and large capacities in Attica to evaluate their compliance with food hygiene standards. The timing of data collection is not related to seasonality; food businesses must follow food hygiene standards throughout the year. The timing of data collection was determined based on preliminary contact with food business operators during the survey design. The inspections were conducted as part of the self-control of the food business for compliance with European regulation 852/2004 on food hygiene and included: (a) the completion of forms and (b) the collection of one water and two food samples for laboratory microbiological analysis for each restaurant establishment. Food business operators should establish and implement food safety programs and procedures based on HACCP principles (European Regulation 852/2004).

Forms. Data were gathered using a predetermined form, which referred to the (procedural) manual of Codex Alimentarius outlining food hygiene standards (CAC/RCP 1-1969/CAC/RCP 39-1993). The evaluation also encompassed identifying unsafe food placement in accordance with Regulation EC/178/2002 on food safety and Greek national legislation (European Commission, 2002; Hellenic Republic, 2006, 2014). More specifically, the following food hygiene factors were investigated: adequacy of catering facilities, equipment requirements, cleaning & disinfection, pest control, personal hygiene, and employee health status, handling of raw materials, water quality, defrosting practices, good cooking practices, apportionment of ready-made food, storage of cooked food in refrigeration and freezing conditions, transport vehicles, reheating processes, unsafe food, and adherence to HACCP record-keeping procedures.

Non-compliances were divided into critical and non-critical (Griffith, 2000). Critical non-compliances in the catering sector are the ones that are likely to lead to the occurrence of foodborne diseases unless these are properly resolved. Such non-compliances involve inadequate heat treatment, storage in inappropriate conditions, cross-contamination, and food handlers who are carriers of pathogens. Non-critical non-compliances involve practices that are not immediately associated with the risk of foodborne diseases but they constitute precautionary measures for the control of environmental conditions, such as poor surface maintenance, improper storage and handling of clean equipment and utensils, etc. (Doğan & Tekiner, 2021; Griffith, 2000; Harris et al., 2014).

WHO sets five critical key points regarding food safety as follows: maintaining cleanliness, keeping raw and cooked food in separate areas, proper cooking, maintaining food temperatures at a safe level, and using safe raw materials and safe water (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations & World Health Organization, 2020; World Health Organization, 2006).

Food and water sampling. Microbiological testing of food and water samples was carried out according to ISO 19458:2006 standard for water quality – sampling for microbiological analysis (International Organization for Standardization, 2006) and ISO 18593-2018 microbiology of the food chain-horizontal methods for surface sampling (International Organisation for Standardisation, 2018).

Statistical analysis. Statistical analysis was performed with IBM-SPSS v26. One-way analysis of variance (1-way ANOVA) and Students' t-test for independent samples were performed to check for statistically significant differences in the mean values between the groups in which catering businesses were categorized (Quick vs full-service restaurants and small, medium, and large restaurants). The results were considered statistically significant when the *p* value was <0.05 and highly significant when the *p* value was <0.0001.

Results

Epidemiological descriptive data of establishments. Inspections were carried out in 74 restaurants and relevant businesses of small, medium, and large capacity in the Attica prefecture (Table 1).

Of them, 57 of 74 (77.03%) were full-service restaurants and 17 of 74 (22.97%) were quick-service restaurants. In terms of geographical distribution, 14 businesses were inspected in the central sector of Athens (10 full-service and 4 quick-service restaurants), in the Northern Sector, 17 businesses (13 full-service restaurants and 4 quick-service restaurants), in the Southern Sector, 22 (17 full-service restaurants and 5 quick service restaurants), in East Attica region, 3 restaurants and 5 quick-service restaurants, in West Attica region, 5 restaurants and in Piraeus, 6 full-service restaurants and 2 quick service restaurants (Graph 1).

Compliance outcomes. The highest rate of non-compliance was observed in the following areas: “adequacy of facilities” (14.12%), “equipment maintenance and sanitization” (12.30%), “pest control” (12.45%), “personal hygiene” (7.58%), and “efficient separation of raw materials” (9.76%). All restaurant businesses under study had an adequate supply of hot and cold potable water although a low rate of non-compliance with the handling of ice (3.79%) was observed. The rates of non-compliance with the other parameters of food hygiene in the restaurant businesses under study (cooking practices, apportionment of meals, storage of cooked food in refrigeration/freezing conditions, transport vehicles, reheating process, etc.) were significantly lower. Moreover, other parameters such as waste management, liquid waste discharges, defrosting practices, etc., presented full compliance. All restaurant businesses under study had developed and implemented HACCP principles and the personnel responsible for food handling have attended the relevant training programs; however, a low rate of non-compliance with record-keeping procedures has been observed (5.86%). A low rate of non-compliance regarding the possession of foods that can be considered unsafe according to Regulation EC/178/2002 and the national legislation has been observed. More specifically, 0.16% were considered harmful to health due to incomplete labeling of allergic substances and 1.56% were inappropriate for consumption in the totality of non-compliances.

To verify self-control procedures in applying the HACCP principles, two food samples were taken from each restaurant, a hot kitchen sample (cooked ready meal) and a cold kitchen (salad). A sample of water was also taken from the food washing area in the preparation room. The parameters analyzed for water quality were: *E. coli*, *enterococci*, *coliforms*, colony count at 22 °C, color, turbidity, taste, smell, pH, and conductivity according to European legislative limits (European Union, 2020). Food samples were examined for aerobic microorganisms at 30 °C, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Salmonella* spp. *Listeria monocytogenes*. All results were within the limits of European legislation on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs (European Commission, 2005).

The inspection results showed that full-service restaurants presented a higher rate of non-compliance compared to quick-service restaurants regarding all types of non-compliance. Medium-sized restaurant businesses present the highest rate (56.41%) of total non-compliance compared to large-sized businesses (29.68%) and small-sized businesses (13.91%); (Table 2) provides a detailed analysis of quantitative non-compliance by category of business size (small, medium, and large), by hygiene standard item.

Geographically, businesses in the southern, northern, and central districts of Athens presented the highest number of non-compliances. The following Table 3 shows the inspection results of non-compliance of restaurant businesses per geographical area of Attica region (numerically and in percentage).

The categories of non-compliance in its totality and for each parameter as indicated by the findings of the inspections in restaurant

Table 1
Business categorization by size (numbers and percentages)

Business Size	Number	Percentage (%)
Large-sized	23	31
Medium-sized	39	53
Small-sized	12	16

businesses during the study period were analyzed. More specifically, regarding the parameter “business size”, it has been observed that medium-sized businesses presented a higher rate of non-compliance in comparison to large-sized businesses (4.08 vs 2.78 respectively) as indicated in Table 4.

The geographical location of the businesses did not present any statistically significant association with all of the non-compliance categories ($P > 0.05$ in all categories of non-compliance) except for the parameter “adequacy of facilities” (Table 5).

The results of the correlation by type of business are indicated in detail in Table 6. More specifically, a statistically significant difference was established between full-service restaurants and quick-service restaurants in the following parameters: Prevention and pest control requirements ($P = 0.015$), equipment requirements ($P = 0.013$), employee health surveillance ($P = 0.005$), non-acceptance of raw materials ($P = 0.003$), efficient separation of raw materials ($P = 0.049$), and food unsuitable for consumption ($P = 0.006$).

Discussion

The novelty of the present study lies in the provision of new data aimed at identifying the risk factors contributing to the occurrence of foodborne diseases originating from restaurant establishments.

According to our findings, the parameter “adequacy of facilities” differed significantly ($P = 0.044$) regarding the business size. Medium-sized businesses presented a higher average rate of non-compliance compared to large-sized sized (4.08 vs 2.78, respectively). Inadequacy of the facilities was associated with failure to store raw materials and finished products in separate areas, poor production flow, lack of a hot water supply, lack of light fixture covers, and insufficient equipment for humidity control. The observed non-compliances can cause cross-contamination of prepared foods by food handlers, direct or indirect contact with raw foods or food processing operations such as cleaning and washing vegetables, washing of equipment and utensils as well as unpacking, storage, or refrigeration of raw materials in the same area (Codex Alimentarius, 1993). Buchholz et al. (2002) also take into consideration the business size as it is considered a factor that may influence food safety (Buchholz et al., 2002).

It appears that the geographical location of the businesses under study did not bear a correlation with food hygiene factors. However, the results of a study conducted in Florida, USA showed that the number of critical non-compliances is influenced by the location of the business (Harris et al., 2014). Another study conducted in Malaysia showed that the location of the business is associated with the prevailing customer perceptions regarding food hygiene (Ungku Fatimah et al., 2011).

The type of business (full service/quick service) played an important role in the correlation between these parameters and non-compliance. More specifically, the number of non-compliances in full-service restaurants was higher in comparison to quick-service restaurants. Similar are the results of a published paper by the National Center of Environmental Health, US CDC (2017) according to which full-service restaurants (restaurants, catering services, nursing homes, and camps) are more often involved in foodborne outbreaks compared to quick-service restaurants (office cafeterias, grocery stores), (Brown et al., 2017). The conclusions of a study by Jin and Lee (2014) according to which full-service restaurants present a higher rate of

Graph 1. Restaurants by geographical area of Attica region.

Table 2

Non-compliance by size of restaurant business (numbers and percentages)

Non-compliance Category	Large	Large (%)	Medium	Medium (%)	Small	Small (%)
Adequacy of Facilities	64	11	159	15	49	18
Equipment Requirements	22	4	34	3	4	1.5
Maintenance and Sanitization of Equipment	58	10	109	10	30	11
Pest Control	86	15	119	11	35	13
Employee Health	19	3	30	3	3	1
Personal Hygiene	38	7	87	8	22	8
Quality of Water and Ice	28	5	35	3	11	4
Non-acceptance of Raw Materials	29	5	31	3	6	2
Inspection/Classification of Raw Materials	28	5	55	5	13	5
Preservation of Raw Materials	19	3	32	3	7	3
Cold Storage of Raw Materials	20	4	50	5	12	4.5
Efficient Separation of Raw Materials	47	8	119	11	23	9
Good Cooking Practice	6	1	22	2	4	1.5
Apportionment of Ready-to-Eat Foods	25	4	44	4	6	2
Refrigeration/Freezing of Cooked Foods	21	4	45	4	12	4.5
Transport Vehicles	0	0	10	1	2	1
Food Reheating Process	15	3	27	3	8	3
Unsafe Food (Harmful Food)	0	0	1	0.1	2	1
Unsafe Food (Unsuitable for Consumption)	13	2	16	1.5	2	1
Record-Keeping Procedures	34	6	62	6	17	6

non-compliance (Jin & Lee, 2014) are similar to the aforementioned. This fact may be due to their offering more complex menus something which entails more procedures than those necessary in quick-service restaurants.

An analysis of the findings showed that the parameter “equipment requirements” is significantly associated with the type of business ($P = 0.013$) and more specifically, full-service restaurants demonstrated a higher average rate of non-compliance in comparison to quick-service restaurants (0.94 vs 0.45). Non-compliance regarding equipment requirements was associated with non-resistant equipment (wooden surfaces) that could not be disinfected and with equipment positioned in a way that does not allow for adequate cleaning and disinfection. The factor of on-resistant equipment (wooden surfaces) is also mentioned in a study by Legnani et al. (2004) regarding catering businesses. Lack of temperature calibration was also observed in some cases. Non-compliance with the maintenance and the sanitization of the equipment that comes into contact with food as well as surfaces that do not come into contact with food (floors, walls, roofs) were also very often observed. A study by Jones et al. refers to non-compliance

regarding surfaces that do not come into contact with foods (poorly maintained floors, walls, and roofs), (Jones et al., 2004). Poor sanitization of the equipment is also referred to in the findings of a study in Turkey according to which improper food handling is associated with poor sanitization of the equipment (Baş et al., 2006). Another study in Ohio, USA makes reference to the use of unsuitable non-industrial equipment (Kassa et al., 2010). Moreover, in another study carried out by Green and Selman, issues related to equipment have been cited as the most frequently reported factor that influences the personnel’s ability to monitor the preservation of foods at appropriate temperatures (Green & Selman, 2005). Equipment must be sufficiently resistant in order to allow maintenance, cleaning, and disinfection for the prevention of cross-contamination (Codex Alimentarius, 2023).

The parameter “pest control” was significantly related to the type of business ($P = 0.015$) and more specifically full-service restaurants present a higher average number of non-compliance (3.50 vs 2.55) in comparison to quick-service restaurants. There were no signs of pest infestation. Non-compliance with insect and rodent control was observed regarding the improper installation of the equipment which

Table 3
Inspection results of non-compliance per geographical area of Attica region (numerically and in percentage)

	Athens (central district)	East Attica	Northern District	West Attica	Southern District	Piraeus and the Islands
Adequacy of facilities	64 (16%)	10 (9%)	70 (15%)	15 (11%)	84 (16%)	29 (13%)
Equipment requirements	13 (3%)	3 (3%)	18 (4%)	4 (3%)	13 (2%)	8 (3.5%)
Maintenance & sanitization of equipment	43 (11%)	12 (11%)	43 (9%)	14 (10%)	62 (11.5%)	20 (9%)
Pest control	49 (12%)	14 (12%)	51 (11%)	21 (15%)	72 (13%)	30 (13%)
Employee health	8 (2%)	3 (3%)	12 (2.5%)	3 (2%)	18 (3%)	8 (3.5%)
Personal hygiene	29 (7%)	9 (8%)	40 (8%)	6 (4%)	44 (8%)	18 (8%)
Quality of water & ice	12 (3%)	4 (3.5%)	20 (4%)	5 (4%)	22 (4%)	10 (4%)
Non-acceptance of raw materials	10 (2.5%)	3 (3%)	23 (5%)	8 (6%)	14 (3%)	8 (3.5%)
Inspection/classification of raw materials	18 (4.5%)	8 (7%)	24 (5%)	9 (6.5%)	28 (5%)	9 (4%)
Preservation of raw materials	12 (3%)	3 (3%)	16 (3%)	5 (4%)	15 (3%)	6 (3%)
Cool storage of raw materials	18 (4.5%)	6 (5%)	18 (4%)	7 (5%)	22 (4%)	11 (5%)
Efficient separation of raw materials	40 (10%)	13 (11.5%)	49 (10%)	10 (7%)	47 (9%)	29 (13%)
Good cooking practice	7 (2%)	2 (2%)	7 (1.5%)	2 (1%)	7 (1%)	7 (3%)
Apportionment of ready-to-eat meals	21 (5%)	4 (3.5%)	20 (4%)	7 (5%)	14 (3%)	9 (4%)
Refrigeration/freezing of cooked foods	16 (4%)	5 (4%)	19 (4%)	4 (3%)	21 (4%)	12 (5%)
Transport vehicles	4 (1%)	0 (0%)	2 (0.4%)	2 (1%)	4 (1%)	0 (0%)
Reheating process	8 (2%)	5 (4%)	13 (3%)	3 (2%)	13 (2%)	8 (3.5%)
Unsafe food (harmful)	3 (1%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Unsafe food (unsuitable)	6 (1.5%)	1 (1%)	9 (2%)	4 (3%)	7 (1%)	3 (1%)
Record-keeping procedures	21 (5%)	8 (7%)	29 (6%)	7 (5%)	34 (6%)	14 (6%)
Total number of businesses inspected	14 (19%)	8 (10.5%)	17 (23%)	5 (7%)	22 (30%)	8 (10.5%)

Table 4
Parameter “adequacy by size of facilities”

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Small	12	4.08	1.379	0.398	3.21	4.96	3	8
Medium	39	4.08	2.333	0.374	3.32	4.83	0	9
Large	23	2.78	1.678	0.350	2.06	3.51	0	6
Total	74	3.68	2.081	0.242	3.19	4.16	0	9

Table 5
Non-compliance by business size

Parameters of Non-Compliance	Business size			
	Small Mean	Medium Mean	Large Mean	Total Mean
Adequacy of Facilities	4.08	4.08	2.78	3.68
Equipment Requirements	0.33	0.87	0.96	0.81
Maintenance and Sanitization of Equipment (cleaning/disinfection)	2.50	2.79	2.52	2.66
Prevention and Pest Control	2.92	3.05	3.74	3.24
Employee Health surveillance	0.25	0.77	0.83	0.70
Personal Hygiene	1.83	2.23	1.65	1.99
Quality of Water – Ice	0.92	0.90	1.22	1.00
Non-acceptance of Raw Material	0.50	0.79	1.26	0.89
Inspection/Classification of Raw Materials	1.08	1.41	1.22	1.30
Preservation of Raw Materials	0.58	0.82	0.83	0.78
Cold Storage of Raw Materials	1.00	1.28	0.87	1.11
Efficient Separation of Raw Materials	1.92	3.05	2.04	2.55
Good Cooking Practice	0.33	0.56	0.26	0.43
Apportionment of Ready-to-Eat Meals	0.50	1.13	1.09	1.01
Refrigeration/Freezing of Cooked Foods	1.00	1.15	0.91	1.05
Transport Vehicles	0.17	0.26	0.00	0.16
Reheating Process	0.67	0.69	0.65	0.68
Unsafe – Harmful Food	0.17	0.03	0.00	0.04
Unsafe food –Unsuitable for Consumption	0.17	0.41	0.57	0.42
Record Keeping	1.42	1.59	1.48	1.53

allows pest infestation. Non-compliance was also observed regarding the improper installation of bait stations/insect traps and the lack of pest control measures. In a study carried out in Turkey (2022), a high level of compliance with pest control in restaurants was observed (Tabak & Ergun, 2022). On the contrary, Schuler et al. suggest that pest control is often ignored by food businesses until their presence and the damage caused by them are revealed (Schuler et al., 1999).

The critical importance of pest control is minimized and can even be rationalized in the financial decisions of the businesses (Fredericks & Henriksen, 2012). Insects and rodents, known carriers of pathogens that can transmit diseases, can carry germs from infected areas to prepared foods and food contact surfaces; therefore, their presence must be prevented in areas of food preparation (Codex Alimentarius, 1993; Hamidi, 2018).

Table 6
Statistical correlation by type of business

Type of Food Business		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P value
Adequacy of Facilities	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	3.59	2.159	0.294	0.547
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	3.90	1.889	0.422	
Equipment Requirements	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	0.94	0.738	0.100	0.013
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	0.45	0.759	0.170	
Maintenance and Sanitization of Equipment (cleaning/disinfection)	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	2.70	1.355	0.184	0.656
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	2.55	1.191	0.266	
Prevention and Pest Control Requirements	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	3.50	1.526	0.208	0.015
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	2.55	1.234	0.276	
Employee Health surveillance	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	0.85	0.787	0.107	0.005
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	0.30	0.571	0.128	
Personal Hygiene	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	1.85	1.365	0.186	0.194
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	2.35	1.663	0.372	
Quality of Water – Ice	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	1.02	0.714	0.097	0.712
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	0.95	0.686	0.153	
Non-acceptance of Raw Materials	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	1.07	1.096	0.149	0.003
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	0.40	0.681	0.152	
Inspection/Classification of Raw Materials	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	1.33	0.971	0.132	0.605
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	1.20	1.005	0.225	
Preservation of Raw Materials	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	0.78	0.502	0.068	0.860
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	0.80	0.410	0.092	
Cold Storage of Raw Material	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	1.13	1.065	0.145	0.689
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	1.05	0.605	0.135	
Efficient Separation of Raw Materials	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	2.87	2.315	0.315	0.049
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	1.70	1.976	0.442	
Good Cooking Practice	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	0.50	0.694	0.094	0.164
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	0.25	0.639	0.143	
Apportionment of Ready-to-Eat Meals	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	1.15	1.106	0.150	0.081
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	0.65	0.988	0.221	
Refrigeration/Freezing of Cooked Foods	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	1.17	1.042	0.142	0.119
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	0.75	0.910	0.204	
Transport Vehicles	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	0.09	0.401	0.055	0.218
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	0.35	0.875	0.196	
Reheating Process	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	0.63	0.734	0.100	0.372
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	0.80	0.696	0.156	
Unsafe – Harmful Food	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	0.04	0.272	0.037	0.850
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	0.05	0.224	0.050	
Unsafe food – Food Unsuitable for Consumption	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	0.52	0.746	0.101	0.006
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	0.15	0.366	0.082	
Record Keeping	Restaurant (Full Service)	54	1.54	0.573	0.078	0.809
	Restaurant (Quick Service)	20	1.50	0.607	0.136	

The parameter “employee health surveillance” was significantly related to the type of business ($P = 0.005$) and more specifically to full-service restaurants which present a higher average number of observations compared to quick-service restaurants (0.85 vs 0.30). Non-compliance with the parameter “employee health surveillance” was related to a lack of pre-employment medical examination certificates (lack of health certificates). Employees can transmit diseases such as hepatitis A virus, norovirus infections, typhoid fever, shigellosis, and amoebic dysentery (Cliver, 1997; County of Orange – California Health Care Agency, 2023; Roukas, 1994; Stein & Chirilă, 2017). People suffering from contagious diseases should report the disease or the symptoms of the disease to the management immediately (Codex Alimentarius, 2023; Codex Alimentarius, 2003).

Two parameters significantly associated with the handling of raw materials handling were observed, and more specifically, “non-acceptance of raw materials” and “efficient separation of raw materials” were significantly associated with the type of business ($P = 0.003$ and $P = 0.049$, respectively). In particular, full-service restaurants present a higher average number in comparison to quick-

service restaurants (1.07 vs 0.40 and 3.50 vs 2.55, respectively). According to Osimani *et al.*, it has been observed that cooked foods and raw products were not separated appropriately, suggesting a potential risk of cross-contamination between raw materials and ready-to-eat foods (Osimani *et al.*, 2018). Raw materials or ingredients should not be accepted by the catering business if it is known that they contain harmful organisms, microorganisms, or toxic, decomposed, or foreign matter that will not be reduced to acceptable levels by normal food preparation processes. Good hygiene practices should also be followed for the prevention of cross-contamination (Codex Alimentarius, 1993; Codex Alimentarius, 2003).

The parameter “foods unsuitable for consumption” was significantly associated with the type of business ($P = 0.006$), and more specifically, full-service restaurants presented a higher number of non-compliance cases compared to quick-service restaurants (0.52 vs 0.15). The non-compliance observed during the inspections was related to foods with altered organoleptic characteristics (presence of mold) and the presence of foreign matter that renders them unacceptable. Food business management should proceed to the with-

drawal of unsafe food and the prevention of further processing and releasing for consumption. Foods that may be classified as unsafe according to the EU and Greek food law, should not be placed on the market (European Commission, 2002, 2010; Hellenic Republic, 2006, 2014).

The businesses under study had developed a HACCP plan and also the procedures, the frequency, and the personnel that is responsible for monitoring the procedures; however, a low rate of non-compliance (5.86%) with record-keeping procedures has been observed. Similar findings by Legnani *et al.* regarding the lack of HACCP record-keeping procedures are also reported (Legnani *et al.*, 2004). Monitoring HACCP procedures does not lie only in record-keeping but also constitutes a basic part of the verification procedures. The results of the inspections can contribute to corrective actions as well as the revision of HACCP procedures management (Arvanitoyannis & Tzouros, 2006; Osimani *et al.*, 2018; Surak & Wilson, 2014).

The present study has specific limitations. The sampled restaurant businesses are just a small portion taken from the list of cooperating businesses of the food inspector's consulting company, which emphasizes self-regulation in relation to food law. Therefore, it may not be representative of the total of restaurant businesses in Attica.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates that restaurant businesses comply with food hygiene and safety standards to a satisfactory level. Small-sized businesses present greater compliance compared to medium-sized and large-sized businesses. Full-service restaurants are associated with a higher number of non-compliances in comparison to quick-service restaurants. However, food business operators must ensure better compliance with factors that may lead to the emergence of foodborne outbreaks (poor design and production flow, lack of adequate facilities and proper equipment, conditions that may lead to cross-contamination, employees' health certificates, better handling of raw materials, and potentially unsafe food within the food business).

These findings may be evaluated for future research in the field of restaurants aiming at improving regarding their compliance with hygiene standards. Restaurant business operators can also focus their attention on more frequent internal inspections and further training of the personnel in the parameters where inadequacies are observed. Additional research for a better understanding of business compliance with hygiene and food safety standards and the evaluation of inspections as a food hygiene tool is required.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Authors' contributions

OC conducted the inspections and collected the relevant data, DK and EC processed the data, EC highlighted the subject according to the literature and wrote the manuscript. GC conducted the statistical analysis. DK, PP, FK, MG, ID, VP, and PL reviewed the draft document and added the relevant references. NT, VP, AL, and NK had the scientific supervision.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Patient consent for publication

Not applicable.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

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